

How can we understand students' needs and expectations in online courses to improve their engagement and learning experience?

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Abstract. Understanding the needs and expectations of students in online courses is critical for improving satisfaction, fostering engagement, and increasing academic success. This paper explores these factors through empirical research. After reviewing existing literature on student needs and expectations in online learning, the paper examines key issues influencing student satisfaction, with a particular focus on Learning Management Systems (LMS). It identifies research gaps and highlights critical factors affecting student engagement. The paper presents the results of an empirical study conducted to collect data directly from computer science students about their needs and expectations of online courses. The research methodology includes a survey of 49 university students who participated in online courses. It includes questions about students' experiences with online courses, how they perceive the organization and implementation of online courses, which activities are most useful to them, and questions providing insight into students' expectations for future online courses. The study also explores the role of social and emotional aspects of online learning, such as the importance of building a community and interacting with peers, in shaping the overall learning experience and compares the results with previous related work that has examined the impact of integrating social networks into e-learning on student satisfaction. Findings highlight the need for a student-centered approach to online course design. This research lays the foundation for future work aimed at developing recommendations for managing student engagement and proposes a novel online course model. This model integrates features of both LMS and social media to enhance sustainability, inclusivity, and scalability in online education.

Keywords: Online Courses, Engagement, Students' Needs.

1 Introduction

As online education becomes increasingly prevalent, especially in the wake of global disruptions like the COVID-19 pandemic, educators and institutions are striving to adapt to the unique challenges and opportunities presented by virtual learning

environments. Central to this adaptation is the recognition that student satisfaction and engagement are pivotal components influencing academic outcomes in online settings. Student satisfaction in online learning is multifaceted, encompassing elements such as course design, instructor interaction, technological infrastructure, and the availability of support resources. Research indicates that when students perceive their online courses as well-structured and interactive, their satisfaction levels tend to increase, which in turn positively affects their academic performance [1], [2], [3]. Engagement in online learning environments is another critical factor that directly correlates with student success. Active engagement strategies, such as collaborative projects, interactive discussions, and real-time feedback, have been shown to enhance learning experiences and outcomes [4], [5], [6].

The integration of Learning Management Systems (LMS) plays a significant role in shaping both satisfaction and engagement in online education. LMS platforms provide a centralized hub for course materials, assessments, and communication, facilitating a structured and accessible learning experience [7], [8], [9]. Research has also explored the role of social media and social networking sites in education, particularly in online learning contexts. Studies indicate that integrating social media into learning environments can enhance student interaction, collaboration, and knowledge-sharing, leading to higher engagement and motivation [10], [11], [12], [13]. Despite the benefits of both LMS and social media in online learning, there remains a significant gap in effectively integrating these systems into a unified digital learning environment. While LMS platforms offer structure, organization, and formal assessment tools, they often lack the dynamic and interactive elements of social media that foster student engagement. Conversely, social media platforms encourage participation and collaboration but may not provide the necessary framework for academic rigor and structured learning pathways. Addressing this gap presents an opportunity to create a hybrid model that incorporates the strengths of both systems.

The primary goal of this paper is to identify critical factors that influence student satisfaction and engagement, with a special focus on the role of LMS platforms. Insights from this study are expected to contribute to the design of student-centred model for online courses that not only enhance learning outcomes but also promote inclusivity and scalability in online education by leveraging the structured approach of LMS systems while incorporating the interactive and community-driven aspects of social media.

This paper is structured as follows: Chapter 2 gives a brief review of recent work on student satisfaction, engagement, and the use of LMS in online learning environments; Chapter 3 outlines the research design, including participant selection, data collection methods, and analytical approaches; Chapter 4 presents the results of the empirical study; Chapter 5 gives some discussion on the findings and research limitations; and finally Chapter 6 summarizes main conclusions and gives some considerations for future research.

2 Related work

Student satisfaction in online learning is influenced by multiple interrelated factors, each playing a crucial role in shaping the overall learning experience. One of the most significant predictors of satisfaction is learner-content interaction, where engaging and well-structured materials enhance perceived course value and foster deeper learning [14], [15]. Instructor presence also plays a crucial role, as students report higher satisfaction when instructors provide continuous support and meaningful interactions [14], [16], [17]. Course structure and design significantly influence satisfaction, with well-organized content, clear objectives, and intuitive navigation improving students' perceptions of course quality [18], [19]. Engagement, both cognitive and emotional, further mediates satisfaction, as active participation in discussions and assignments fosters a sense of connection and motivation [16], [20]. Technological reliability is another critical factor. Seamless, user-friendly platforms enhance the learning experience, while technical issues can lead to frustration and disengagement [16], [21]. Lastly, self-efficacy and autonomy contribute positively to satisfaction, as students who feel confident and capable of managing their own learning tend to be more motivated and successful [14], [22]. Student engagement in online learning is influenced by social, technological, pedagogical, and motivational factors. A strong sense of community and social support from instructors enhance participation by increasing students' confidence in their academic abilities [23]. Instructor engagement, reflected in responsiveness and active participation, directly influences student motivation and interaction as well [24].

The integration of LMS plays a crucial role in shaping student satisfaction and engagement in online education. Key functionalities such as ease of use, communication tools, and personalized learning paths significantly influence learning experiences. Students' perception of LMS ease of use and usefulness is a major determinant of satisfaction. System characteristics, well-structured course design, and instructor support all contribute to a seamless learning experience [25], [26]. Communication and interaction within LMS platforms further enhance engagement, as effective feedback mechanisms and interactive course structures foster meaningful connections between students and instructors [27]. Integrating social media features into LMS is known to help improve usability, communication, and personalization, thereby enhancing student engagement and satisfaction. Regarding the usability enhancements, familiar interfaces, such as those resembling Facebook, are preferred by students for communication, making LMS more user-friendly [28]. Additionally, the ease of use of social media platforms can be transferred to LMS, improving overall user experience [11], [29]. Social media also facilitates better communication and interaction between students and instructors, with students more likely to engage in these environments [10], [28], [30]. By aligning with students' preferred communication styles and fostering a sense of community, integrating social media features creates a more student-centered LMS that boosts engagement and promotes collaborative learning, which is linked to improved academic performance and satisfaction.

3 Methodology

Students' attitudes and opinions on their needs and expectations of online courses and the impact of using LMS on their satisfaction in the e-learning environment were tested using a questionnaire survey. A survey was distributed via Google Forms and a Moodle-based LMS to students in all three years of a bachelor's degree program in computer science, as well as both years of a master's degree program. Students from different academic years took part in a survey in the winter semester of the academic year 2024/2025. Since the survey was open for two weeks, completely anonymous, voluntary, and posed no risk to participants, formal informed consent was not required. Students were free to decide whether or not to participate. Prior to completing the survey, participants were provided with detailed information regarding the research context, its purpose, the procedures involved, the anonymity of responses, and the potential benefits of participation. The number of participating students was 49 (out of a total of 414 students enrolled in all study programs).

The survey consisted of 14 questions, including 3 open-ended and 11 closed-ended questions. The closed-ended items comprised yes/no questions (e.g. *Do you consider the course materials understandable, interactive, multimedia enriched and available on time?*), multiple-response options (e.g. *What activities do you consider the best for learning?*, or *How often would you participate in interactive activities?*), and items measured on a 5-point Likert scale (e.g. *Determine to what extent, in your experience, the listed elements were achieved through e-courses.*). The survey is available in Croatian language on this link. The survey questions were used to test the main research questions, which were: "*How does the integration of specific LMS functionalities play a role in shaping engagement and better learning experience in online education?*" (RQ1), and "*What are students' perceptions on the ways LMS features could be optimized for improving their learning experience and engagement?*" (RQ2).

The questionnaire was divided into 6 main areas of interest: 1) general characteristics, 2) experiences with online courses, 3) organization of online courses, 4) activities in online courses, 5) implementation of online courses, and 6) functionalities of LMS. The survey results were recorded and semi-automatically processed using both Google Forms and the statistical tool IBM SPSS Statistics Version 29. Closed questions were processed automatically by the system, but the open questions were processed manually by the authors by sorting the answers into relevant categories using Microsoft Office Excel 2021.

4 Results

A total of 49 participants took part in the study, 40 of them are at the undergraduate level of study and 9 at the graduate level. All faculty's courses are delivered in a hybrid format, combining face-to-face lectures in the classroom with online learning, which may be conducted synchronously or asynchronously. Each course includes a total of 30 hours of lectures and 30 hours of practical exercises per semester. The maximum proportion of online lectures per course is limited to 40%. The online component is

delivered primarily in an asynchronous format, in accordance with university guidelines, and includes a variety of teaching materials, interactive lessons, discussion forums, and self-assessment activities within the LMS. A smaller portion of the online instruction is conducted synchronously, typically for activities such as project presentations or laboratory exercises. In accordance with this approach, all students are required to utilize a Moodle-based LMS platform for each course they are enrolled in.

Participants were asked how they would rate their overall experience with online courses so far, and 41 out of 49 students (84%) state that they are satisfied or fully satisfied with the overall experience. Only one student is not satisfied, and 7 are neither satisfied nor unsatisfied. When asked about the importance of various elements of online course organization, **participants agree that regular and timely communication with teachers is the most important, followed by the quality and clarity of teaching materials, the alignment of activities with assessment requirements and the technical simplicity and user-friendliness of the e-learning platform.** On the other hand, access to additional resources (recommended books, articles, video materials) received the lowest rating. Details are presented in table 1.

Table 1. Mean values for elements of online course organization

Elements of online course organization	Means (1-5)	Std. dev.
Clearly defined learning objectives and outcomes	4.39	1.10
Course structure (weekly plans, modules)	4.35	0.88
Regular and timely communication with teachers	4.78	0.51
Teacher availability for questions and support	4.27	0.95
Quality and clarity of teaching materials	4.63	0.64
Flexibility of schedules for students with diverse commitments	4.12	1.01
Access to additional resources (books, articles, video materials)	3.43	1.12
Frequency and quality of feedback on assignments and activities	4.22	0.85
Alignment of activities with assessment requirements	4.45	0.82
Integration of digital tools (e.g., interactive platforms, simulations)	3.88	1.03
Technical simplicity and user-friendliness of the e-learning platform	4.45	0.82

Furthermore, the study also examined the quality of the online course materials. Most participants perceive the materials as sufficiently comprehensible, adequately interactive, and enriched with multimedia. Additionally, they agree that all materials are made available on time. Detailed findings are presented in figure 1.

Fig. 1. Student' perceptions of online course materials

Regarding the types of activities (Figure 2), participants consider **online tests and quizzes to be the most useful for their learning (67%), followed by video lectures (51%) and interactive exercises (45%)**. The least useful activities, according to the participants, are forum discussions (4%) and the writing of essays and papers (14%).

Fig. 2. Perception of most useful activities for learning

When participants were asked how frequently they would like to engage in interactive activities such as discussions or group tasks, only 3 participants expressed a preference for weekly participation, 11 preferred every two weeks, 19 once a month, and 14 would prefer less frequently than that. This indicates that **over 70% of participants would engage in interactive activities once a month or less**, which is surprising given that approximately 45% of participants consider interactive tasks and simulations to be among the most important activities for learning.

To answer the **RQ1 about the role of LMS functionalities in shaping engagement and better learning experience**, participants rated the elements of online course implementation based on their own experiences. Figure 3 illustrates the perceived extent of achievement for each element, with a rating of 1 indicating that the element was not achieved at all in the online courses, and a rating of 5 indicating that it was fully achieved. Participants believe that nearly all elements were successfully implemented in the online courses (more than 50% of participants consider elements to be achieved or fully achieved), **except for the ability to communicate in real-time and the possibility of informal communication with teachers, which received ratings lower than 50%**. The highest-rated element is the accessibility of materials and activities, with 90% of participants considering it to be achieved or fully achieved. This is followed by the flexibility in organizing one's own time, with 82% agreement.

Participants were also asked to rate the functionalities of the LMS, with 1 representing "very poor" and 5 representing "very good." Table 2 presents the mean values of the participants' answers along with the corresponding standard deviations. From this data, it can be concluded that the **highest-rated functionalities are the ease of navigation and content discovery and the integration of additional tools** (e.g., quizzes, forums, assignments, video content, games, wikis, webinars, etc.), both with a mean value of 4.18. This is followed by the loading speed of materials and activities with a mean value of 4.10. The **lowest-rated functionality is enjoyable activities for study breaks**, with an average score of 2.53, but majority of other functionalities, such as **user experience on mobile devices, availability of real-time communication, informal learning and additional resources, ability to engage in informal**

communication with peers and professors, and opportunity to create and participate in virtual communities or groups, also scored low (below 3.80).

Fig. 3. Ratings of the elements of online course implementation

Table 2. Mean values for LMS functionalities

LMS functionalities	Means (1-5)	Std. dev.
Ease of navigation and content discovery	4,18	0,95
System stability (free from technical issues and interruptions)	4,04	0,98
Loading speed of materials and activities	4,10	1,07
Integration of additional tools (e.g., quizzes, video, games, wikis, etc.)	4,18	1,05
User experience on mobile devices	3,35	1,11
Availability of real-time communication	3,51	1,02
Informal learning and additional resources	3,78	1,09
Ability to engage in informal communication with peers and professors	3,39	1,20
Opportunity to create and participate in virtual communities or groups	3,41	1,02
Enjoyable activities for study breaks	2,53	1,21

To answer the **RQ2 about students' perceptions on the ways LMS features could be optimized for improving their learning experience and engagement**, it was necessary to qualitatively analyse the open-end questions from the survey. The qualitative results indicate that the most frequently mentioned advantage of online and hybrid courses is **flexibility**, with participants emphasizing the ability to manage their own time and study at their own pace. Participants also value the option to revisit video lectures and explanations, which supports individualized learning. Access to materials

is another key benefit, as participants highlighted the ease of obtaining essential resources, the ability to review content multiple times, and the availability of recorded lectures for complex topics. Regarding challenges in online and hybrid courses, participants identified issues with locating and organizing learning resources, particularly when materials are not clearly structured. Some participants mentioned concerns about the reliability of task submissions and the accumulation of coursework if regular assessments are not conducted. Additionally, participants highlighted problems with understanding complex topics without direct guidance and the difficulty of managing deadlines, especially when multiple important tasks converge within the same period. Despite these challenges, 33% of participants reported no significant difficulties, emphasizing that they find the online environment manageable with proper organization and accessible resources.

The results regarding participants' emotional responses when accessing online course platforms reveal a spectrum of feelings, with satisfaction being the most prevalent. Participants reported **feeling satisfied due to the accessibility of materials and the organized structure of the platform**. Some participants expressed **feelings of motivation**, particularly when the course content was well-structured and engaging. However, some participants indicated feelings of uncertainty, often linked to doubts about task completion and the accuracy of their submissions. Frustration was also mentioned, especially regarding **unclear instructions and the lack of immediate feedback** from teachers. Few participants reported feelings of concern or anxiety, particularly when accessing grades or managing deadlines. Neutral responses were also common, with several participants stating that their emotional reaction depended on the specific course or task. Overall, **57% of participants state a positive emotional response, 20% a neutral emotional response, and 23% state a negative emotional response**.

Regarding the functionalities lacking in the current LMS platform, a recurring concern was the **inconsistent structure across different courses**, which complicates navigation. Participants suggested improvements to **mobile accessibility and enhanced calendar features**, such as the ability to export deadlines to external calendars (e.g., iCal files). Other requested functionalities included **group communication spaces for informal student interaction, improved feedback systems where teachers could leave comments on submitted assignments, and public grade tables to foster competition and motivation**.

When asked for concrete suggestions to improve their satisfaction and experience with the LMS platform, participants mentioned again **enhancing the mobile version to align with the desktop experience**. Several participants suggested the addition of **more interactive learning materials**, such as self-assessment quizzes and video content, to facilitate knowledge retention. Improved communication tools were also a recurring theme, with requests for **better chat spaces** that support multimedia attachments and clearer teacher contact information, including office hours.

5 Discussion and limitations

The integration of specific LMS functionalities is crucial in enhancing engagement and fostering an improved learning experience in online education. The findings of this study indicate the need for further enhancement of functionalities that facilitate real-time communication and enjoyable activities for study breaks, which aligns more closely with the communication patterns commonly found in social media environments. This result is in line with an earlier study that investigated the effects of integrating social networks into e-learning [10] which found that real-time communication significantly impacts student satisfaction. In their research, 68% of participants indicated that real-time communication would positively influence their studies, yet less than half felt this was adequately achieved in their online courses. Similarly, informal communication with teachers via social networks was positively received by 45% of students, though only 41% felt this was sufficiently implemented.

The findings highlight the potential benefits of incorporating social media characteristics into LMS platforms. Features such as real-time communication, informal interaction with peers and instructors, enjoyable activities for study breaks and multimedia-rich content can emulate the dynamic and engaging environment of social networks. This approach can foster a sense of community, enhance student engagement, and improve the overall learning experience by making it more interactive and responsive to students' needs.

Like any study, this research has certain limitations. It was conducted within a specific timeframe and among a limited sample of students, which may affect the generalizability of the findings to other populations or educational settings. Expanding the research over a longer period and across multiple faculties could offer deeper insights and more reliable conclusions. Additionally, as the study focused on students from a single faculty, the results may not fully capture the diversity of experiences across different disciplines where online learning dynamics can vary significantly. Finally, while survey anonymity ensured honest feedback, it also limited the ability to follow up on specific responses for further clarification.

6 Conclusions and future work

This paper highlights key factors affecting student engagement and the learning experience, with a particular emphasis on the role of LMS platforms. The results from the study reveal significant insights into students' perceptions of online courses, emphasizing both advantages and challenges. Flexibility, access to materials, and the ability to revisit lectures were highlighted as key benefits, while issues with organizing resources, reliability of submissions, and managing deadlines were notable challenges. Participants' emotional responses indicated a generally positive experience, though uncertainty and frustration were also present. The findings suggest that while online learning offers substantial benefits, improvements in LMS structure, mobile accessibility, and communication tools are crucial for enhancing student engagement and learning experience. The study underscores the importance of enhancing features that support real-

time communication and provide enjoyable study break activities, reflecting the interactive nature of social media environments. Integrating these specific functionalities is essential for increasing student engagement and improving the online learning experience. The findings advocate for a student-centred approach to online course design that balances structured content delivery with interactive, community-driven engagement. Future research will focus on further refining recommendations for managing student satisfaction in online environments, with an emphasis on the development of a comprehensive e-learning model. This includes designing and testing a novel online course framework that merges LMS functionalities with social media elements to create an engaging, interactive, and structured learning space. Ultimately, these efforts will contribute to the conceptualization and development of a unified platform aimed at improving student engagement, fostering a sense of community, and supporting academic success through a holistic and adaptive online learning experience.

Acknowledgments. The research has been co-funded by “uniri-iskusni-drustv-23-209 (3203)” under the project “Development of an e-learning course design model based on recommendations for managing student satisfaction in higher education”.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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